

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 29

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 29

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 29:0 A Psalm of David.</p>	<p>Psa. 29:1 מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד הַבּוֹ</p>
<p>Psa. 29:1 "Ascribe to the LORD, O ¹sons of the mighty,</p>	<p>לְיְהוָה בְּנֵי אֱלֹהִים הַבּוֹ לְיְהוָה כְּבוֹד וְעֹז : ² הַבּוֹ לְיְהוָה כְּבוֹד</p>
<p>Ascribe to the LORD glory and strength.</p>	<p>שְׁמוֹ הַשְׁתַּחֲוֵי לְיְהוָה בְּהַרְדֵּת-</p>
<p>² Ascribe to the LORD the glory ¹due to His name;</p>	<p>קִדְשׁ : ³ קוֹל יְהוָה עַל-הַמַּיִם</p>
<p>Worship the LORD ^ain ²holy array.</p>	<p>אֶל-הַכְּבוֹד הַרְעִים יְהוָה עַל-</p>
<p>Psa. 29:3 The ^avoice of the LORD is upon the waters;</p>	<p>מַיִם רַבִּים : ⁴ קוֹל-יְהוָה בַּכַּחַ</p>
<p>The God of glory ^bthunders, The LORD is over ¹many waters.</p>	<p>קוֹל יְהוָה בְּהַרְדֵּר : ⁵ קוֹל יְהוָה</p>
<p>⁴ The voice of the LORD is ^apowerful,</p>	<p>שִׁבַּר אַרְזִים וַיִּשְׁבַּר יְהוָה אֶת-</p>
<p>The voice of the LORD is majestic.</p>	<p>אַרְזֵי הַלְבָנוֹן : ⁶ וַיִּרְקִיעֵם כְּמוֹ-</p>
<p>⁵ The voice of the LORD breaks the cedars;</p>	<p>עֵגֶל לְבָנוֹן וְשָׂרִיז כְּמוֹ בֶן-</p>
<p>Yes, the LORD breaks in pieces ^athe cedars of Lebanon.</p>	<p>רֵאמִים : ⁷ קוֹל-יְהוָה תִּצַּב</p>
<p>⁶ He makes Lebanon ^askip like a calf, And ^bSirion like a young wild ox.</p>	<p>לְהַבּוֹת אֵשׁ : ⁸ קוֹל יְהוָה יִתִּיל</p>
<p>⁷ The voice of the LORD hews out ¹flames of fire.</p>	<p>מִדְבַר יִתִּיל יְהוָה מִדְבַר קִדְשׁ :</p>
<p>⁸ The voice of the LORD ¹shakes the wilderness;</p>	<p>קוֹל יְהוָה וַיִּחַלֵּל אֵילֹת</p>
<p>The LORD shakes the wilderness of ^aKadesh.</p>	<p>וַיִּחַשְׁשֶׁף יַעֲרוֹת וּבְהִיכְלוֹ כָּלוּ</p>
<p>⁹ The voice of the LORD makes ^athe deer to calve</p>	<p>אֵמַר כְּבוֹד : ¹⁰ יְהוָה לַמַּבּוּל</p>
<p>And strips the forests bare; And ^bin His temple everything</p>	<p>יֵשֵׁב וַיִּנְשַׁב יְהוָה מִלֶּדֶךְ לְעוֹלָם :</p>
<p>says, "Glory!"</p>	<p>יְהוָה עֹז לְעַמּוֹ יִתֵּן יְהוָה יְבַרֵךְ אֶת-עַמּוֹ בְּשִׁלּוֹם :</p>

<p>Psa. 29:10 The LORD sat <i>as King</i> at the ^aflood; Yes, the LORD sits as ^bKing forever.</p> <p>¹¹ The LORD will give ^astrength to His people;</p> <p>²The LORD will bless His people with ^bpeace.</p>	
--	--

References

<p>Psalm 29:1 ¹Or <i>sons of gods</i> ^a1 Chr 16:28, 29; Ps 96:7-9</p> <p>Psalm 29:2 ¹Lit of <i>His name</i> ²Or <i>the majesty of holiness</i> ^a2 Chr 20:21; Ps 110:3</p> <p>Psalm 29:3 ¹Or <i>great</i> ^aPs 104:7 ^bJob 37:4, 5; Ps 18:13 ^cPs 18:16; 107:23</p> <p>Psalm 29:4 ^aPs 68:33</p> <p>Psalm 29:5 ^aJudg 9:15; 1 Kin 5:6; Ps 104:16; Is 2:13; 14:8</p> <p>Psalm 29:6 ^aPs 114:4, 6 ^bDeut 3:9</p> <p>Psalm 29:7 ¹i.e. lightning</p> <p>Psalm 29:8 ¹Or <i>causes...to whirl</i> ^aNum 13:26</p>	<p>Psalm 29:9 ^aJob 39:1 ^bPs 26:8</p> <p>Psalm 29:10 ^aGen 6:17 ^bPs 10:16</p> <p>Psalm 29:11 ¹Or <i>May the LORD give</i> ²Or <i>May the LORD bless</i> ^aPs 28:8; 68:35; Is 40:29 ^bPs 37:11; 72:3</p>
--	--

Targum

Psa. 29:1 A psalm of David. Give praise in the presence of the LORD, O bands of angels; give glory and might in the LORD's presence. ² Give the glory of his name in the presence of the LORD; bow down before the LORD in the splendor of holiness. ³ The voice of the LORD is heard above the waters; in his glorious might the LORD called out over many waters. ⁴ The voice of the LORD is heard in strength; the voice of the LORD is heard in splendor. ⁵ The voice of the LORD shatters cedars; the word of the LORD has shattered the cedars of Lebanon. ⁶ And he made them jump like a calf – Lebanon, and the Mount of Noisome Fruit, like the young of oxen. ⁷ The voice of the LORD splits flames of fire. ⁸ The voice of the LORD shakes the wilderness; the word of the LORD shakes the wilderness of Rekem. ⁹ The voice of the LORD impregnates the hinds, and makes the beasts of the forest give birth; and in his sanctuary above, all his servants say, "Glory," in his presence. ¹⁰ In the generation of the Flood, the LORD sat on his throne of judgment to take vengeance on them; and the LORD sat on the throne of mercy and saved Noah; and he reigns over his children forever and ever. ¹¹ The LORD gave the Torah to his people; the LORD will bless his people in peace.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

David wrote this Psalm in a continuation of Psalm 28. David vows to follow the LORD's Word. He was thankful for everything the LORD gave Him. This Psalm's purpose is to awaken our feelings of devoted obedience to the LORD.

Verse One

בְּנֵי אֱלֹהִים (b'nay Elohim) – means "sons of God." This may have been a call to the people that those who are strong must remember that the LORD gives that gift. As humans, we are "sons of God" and not "God." It reminds us to be humble, especially before the LORD.

הָבִי לַיהוָה כְּבוֹד (havu laAdonai c'dod) – means "ascribe to the LORD glory." Everything within you, your most incredible triumphs, comes from the LORD, and this must always be remembered. Without the LORD, each of us is nothing and would not exist.

A Psalm of David. Ascribe to the LORD all who are endowed with strength, ascribe to the LORD glory and might.

Verse two

The LORD's name must be honored above all names. It was believed that it was through the tetragrammaton that all powers from the LORD were made available to humans.

Ascribe to the LORD the glory due to his name, cast yourself down before the LORD in holiness's beauty.

Verse three

From this point on, the psalmist elaborates on the various manifestations of the LORD's revelation. The psalmist calls this revelation "the voice of the LORD."

The voice of the LORD is on the waters; God of glory thunders; the LORD is heard upon the surging waters.

Verse four

The voice of the LORD can be heard through His Law (the Torah). The LORD charges you to develop all moral potentialities. He also expects us to perfect our talents and faculties.

The voice of the LORD is within every force; His voice is in all beautiful things.

Verse 5, 6, & 7

The voice of the LORD can break through anything.

The voice of the LORD also breaks cedars, even as the LORD broke the cedars of Lebanon.

He makes them skip like calves, Lebanon and Sirion like an ox.

The voice of the LORD also blows out flames of fire.

Verse 8

This verse was a reminder of the events at Mount Sinai when the LORD spoke to the children of Israel.

The voice of the LORD shakes the wilderness; He also shakes the wilderness of Kadesh.

Verse 9

The voice of the LORD has tremendous power to affect what is happening on Earth.

The voice of the LORD makes deer calve, even while it strips the forests bare, and in His Temple, all that is His says "glory."

Verse 10

The LORD sat at the Flood can refer to anytime the LORD sits in judgment and sentences the Earth to some punishment. We need to remember that the LORD is watching the evil and sin in the world.

The LORD sat enthroned at the Flood. The LORD sits as King forever, always watching what we are doing.

Verse 11

The LORD gives strength to his people so that they can continue to praise Him. He also offers to His people peace and tranquility.

To His people, God will grant power to be victorious over all; the LORD will bless His people with peace.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A Psalm of David. Ascribe to the LORD all who are endowed with strength, ascribe to the LORD glory and might.

Ascribe to the LORD the glory due to his name, cast yourself down before the LORD in holiness's beauty.

The voice of the LORD is on the waters; God of glory thunders; the LORD is heard upon the surging waters.

The voice of the LORD is within every force; His voice is in all beautiful things.

The voice of the LORD also breaks cedars, even as the LORD broke the cedars of Lebanon.

He makes them skip like calves, Lebanon and Sirion like an ox.

The voice of the LORD also blows out flames of fire.

The voice of the LORD shakes the wilderness; He also shakes the wilderness of Kadesh.

The voice of the LORD makes deer calve, even while it strips the forests bare, and in His Temple, all that is His says "glory."

The LORD sat enthroned at the Flood. The LORD sits as King forever, always watching what we are doing.

To His people, God will grant power to be victorious over all; the LORD will bless His people with peace.

Appendix

Rev: 1/9/2017 MHK

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

